

DETERMINATION OF INTRINSIC SCATTER IN LIFETIMES OF CARBON FIBRE EPOXY PRESSURE VESSELS IN VIEW OF DEFINING FUNDAMENTAL SAFETY FACTORS

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1 Introduction

There is a pressing need to put safety factors on a quantitative basis for composite pressure vessels so as to ensure their reliable long-term use. Safety factors attempt to bracket the widest possible range of failure conditions but it should be possible to quantify this range in terms of intrinsic damage mechanisms and in-service loads so as to define the minimum scatter which can be experienced. This paper addresses the failure mechanisms in advanced filament wound composites and in particular the role of the viscoelastic resin matrices in controlling both deferred fibre failures and improved fibre alignment. An intrinsic mechanism is the increasing number of fibre breaks, initially randomly distributed but finally leading to clusters of breaks and instability. Carbon fibres seem to show neither time dependent properties, at room temperature, nor sensitivity to fatigue. The fibres are elastic and delayed failure of carbon fibre composites, loaded in the fibre direction, is due to the viscoelastic properties of the matrix. Other types of composites reinforced with glass or aramid type fibres can fail due to delayed failure of the fibres which does not depend on the matrix. Both experimental and modelling data are given in the paper that allow both the intrinsic scatter in composite properties to be evaluated and provide a basis for a quantitative understanding of the minimum safety factors which should be employed. Residual strength is not seen to fall, as in metals, but rather a sudden death situation leads to failure. This can lead to misleading tests of pressure vessels in service in which it is sought to reveal degradation by measuring remaining strength. Composite pressure vessels are made by filament winding around a mandrel, which later becomes a gas proof liner for

the pressure vessel. The fibres are wound on geodesic paths, which ensures that, when the vessel is pressurised, the fibres are only subjected to tensile loads. In this way it is possible to make an analogy with the behaviour of unidirectional composites loaded in the fibre direction.

2 Failure models for unidirectional composites applied to pressure vessels

The failure of unidirectional composites when loaded in the fibre direction is controlled by the failure of the fibres. Typical, approximately 99% of the load is carried by the fibres. In these specimens the fibres have to break for failure to occur.

The consequences of failure of fibres in a composite material have been examined in a number of studies, beginning with Cox who developed a 2-D analytical analysis of load sharing between elastic fibres embedded in an elastic matrix [1]. Cox revealed the fundamental mechanism controlling composite behaviour to be load transfer from the matrix, which undergoes shear near the fibre, to which it is well bonded. The result is that the fibre experiences tensile loads increasing from the fibre's ends. By writing equations of equilibrium between the shear forces in the matrix and the tensile forces in the fibre, Cox was able to provide analytical solutions for the stress states in and around fibre breaks in a composite. More recent studies have considered the effects of fibre failure on the other unbroken fibres in a composite. It has been shown that the effect of a fibre break in a composite was confined to a small volume of material around the break and that only the fibres immediately neighbouring the fibre break experienced any change of stress. With the availability of computers and increasing

computational capacity this situation has been the subject of many subsequent two and three dimensional numerical studies, including a few which consider that the effects of a viscoelastic matrix [2, 3].

2.1 Three dimensional modelling

A multiscale three dimensional model of damage accumulation in unidirectional composites has been developed by the authors and applied to composite pressure vessels. The details of the model are published elsewhere but are outlined here for clarity [4, 5]. It is clear that any attempt to model the behaviour of a complete structure with a discretisation at the level of the individual fibres would encounter unacceptable computational times. Nevertheless the mechanisms which govern failure occur at the scale of the individual fibres. The FE2 (two level) finite element model, which has been developed, provides a multi-scale approach which has been adopted in this study and can be seen to share points in common with other studies [6, 7]. Initially the reinforcing fibres are taken to be perfectly arranged parallel to one another. This is an approximation which will be analysed in a longer version of this paper. The smallest 3D volume that represents all the physical characteristics governing behaviour in the composite has to be defined. Earlier studies have allowed this Representative Volume Element (RVE) to be defined for the undamaged composite, Fig.1 [4].

If the composite is considered to be periodic with a hexagonal fibre arrangement in the X, Y plane, the periodic cell which is representative of the RVE consists of 32 fibres. Its geometry is considered to be a parallelepiped with the Z axis parallel to the fibres and the section is a square with sides of length c . From ref. 4, the length in the Z direction was taken to be between the planes $z = 0$ and $z = L = 8\text{mm}$. The reference origin O is the geometrical centre of the section in the plane $z = 0$. At this scale, at point M, the stress tensor is described as σ and the strain as ϵ .

Earlier studies have shown that this approach accurately describes what happens in the vicinity of a fibre break [4] and as fibres fail, for different levels of damage, can account for:

- the random nature of fibre breaks and the points of failure along the fibre length;

- the number of breaks in a RVE at five levels of damage from the undamaged to the failed state;
- the load transfer to and along the intact fibres neighbouring fibre failures;
- the effects of interfacial debonding around the fibre break on load transfer to intact fibres;
- the effects of the viscoelastic nature of the matrix, taken as linear, on load transfer to neighbouring intact fibres;

The present study also takes into account the local variability of fibre volume fraction. The coefficient of load transfer along the lengths of the fibres is given by the ratio of the stress in the fibre at a given point to the stress state in the undamaged state. In this way the state of damage being considered is calculated with respect to the undamaged state, taking into account; the debonded interfacial length along the broken fibre from its break; the Weibull modulus of the fibres; the local volume fraction, and the time after fibre failure.

The calculation time to sum all the RVEs over the entire structure, whether it is a plate of pressure vessel specimen would be prohibitive so a less time consuming approach is therefore necessary. The load transfer function has been smoothed, assuming a linear function, and only the load transfer in the fibre nearest to the fibre break calculated. In order to separate the effects of interfacial debonding and those due to the viscoelastic shear of the matrix, we put the stress concentration factor equal to the sum of the effect due to the fibres, the interfacial debond and the viscoelastic behaviour of the matrix which tends, with time, to relax the contribution of the matrix around broken fibres.

These smoothed parameters are used as a data base describing the microscopic scale which needs to be taken into account in the multiscale FE2 model. Using the overall stress applied on the macroscopic scale, the duration of the load and the state of damage, this data base allows, by linearity, the stress state in the components at the microscopic scale to be known. The tensile stresses in the fibres can therefore be computed, without resolving the problem at the microscopic scale, by the finite element method and the evolution of the damage, consisting of increasing numbers of fibre breaks in the RVE, can be evaluated. It is assumed that the failure of a fibre induces a debond length of $35\mu\text{m}$, from each broken end, which has been shown to

result in the greatest stress concentration in neighbouring intact fibres [4].

In order to compare the relative influences of different physical phenomena, six levels of refinement in the model have been considered : the first taking into account only fibre breaks; the second adds the effect of load transfer, through the matrix on intact fibres neighbouring the fibre break; the third includes the effects of fibre matrix debonding from the point of failure and then the previous three degrees of refinement are again considered but the viscoelastic nature of the matrix is included. The calculation considers the most critical levels of stress transfer between the broken fibre and its immediate neighbours.

The model indicates that fibre failures initially occur randomly throughout the uniformly stressed specimen. Each break is isolated from its neighbours by the shearing of the matrix around the points of failure. However, as numbers of breaks increase so does the probability of failures occurring at weak points along intact fibres neighbouring the broken fibre. This leads to a coalescence of breaks in the body of the composite and these make the structure unstable. The exact condition for damage coalescence to occur will vary between similar specimens because of the stochastic nature of fibre strengths and the random distribution of the fibre population.

2.2 Comparison between theoretical and experimental results

Initially a simple plate specimen has been considered. The composite had a fibre volume fraction of 64%, the fibres had diameters of 7 μ m and the matrix was viscoelastic epoxy resin matrix. At the macro scale, two types of simulations were made of the behaviour of a plate specimen. First, a tensile test was simulated to determine the ultimate strength of the specimen in a monotonic test and then a constant load test was simulated to evaluate its lifetime under steady loads. In the case considered the steady load test was carried out at 0.85 the ultimate average failure stress.

The input data for this calculation were:

- at the macroscopic scale: the characteristics of the undamaged composite and the law describing the fall in longitudinal rigidity of the equivalent homogeneous material;

- at the microscopic scale, for each Gauss point: the random choice of 5 failure stresses according to the Weibull statistics, which had been shown, experimentally, to describe the stochastic failure strengths of the fibres;

- the data base allowing the axial stresses supported by the fibres in the RVE to be known and the evolution of the damage from the undamaged state to complete failure.

The multiscale simplified FE2 calculation is iterative and calculates the state of damage (number of fibres broken), at the nth steps, having determined the state of damage at step n-1 in the following manner:

- a time increment is considered together with or without a change to the macroscopic stress depending on whether an increase in load is made or whether the test is at constant load;

- the finite element calculation at the macroscopic scale determines the macroscopic stress on the composite in the direction of the fibres;

- looping at the Gauss points for the microscopic scale:

- a localisation step – Knowing the macroscopic stress and the damage state of the material, the data base for load transfer is applied so as to calculate the axial stress in the fibres contained in the RVEs. This stress allows the number of broken fibres in the RVE to develop by comparison with the failure stresses selected from the Weibull analysis;

- a homogenisation step – To calculate the macroscopic behaviour of the homogenised equivalent material taking into account the new state of damage.

- the next incremental step in the iteration process as a function of time can be calculated.

The results obtained for the breaking stress from the tensile test simulation were comparable to the mean failure stress obtained experimentally. The numerical failure stress was calculated as 2200 MPa, which was within 9% of the mean experimental failure stress. When the constant load experiment with the plate specimen loaded to 80% of its failure stress was compared to the creep test simulation under the same loading conditions, very good agreement between theory and experiment was obtained, as shown in Fig.2.

It can be noted that the introduction of the stochastic strength properties of the fibres enables not only the general behaviour of the composite to be predicted

but also the scatter in the results obtained with different, apparently identical specimens.

In order to obtain failures in a reasonable time, it was necessary to consider an applied stress which was higher. Having validated the model at 80% failure stress, the loading of the same type of specimen was raised and simulated to a load of 85% of its failure strength.

Thirty simulations of steady load tests on macroscopically similar unidirectional specimens were carried out. As at the lower stress, delayed failures of fibres occurred and the point at which coalescence of the breaks began varied from one specimen to another. An inflection point in the rate of damage curve corresponding to an increase in damage rate was observed upon reaching the point of coalescence of breaks. This has been discussed in greater detail elsewhere [8].

These points were used to trace a probability curve of failure as a function of in-service life, as shown in Fig.3 [8].

Impressively, the first inflection point occurred after around 15 years; however, five specimens were calculated not to show a point of inflection after 25 years. Figure 3 shows that although none of the thirty simulated tests showed that the instability point was reached in less than fifteen years the probability of failure, as required by industry, of one failure in a million specimens every fifteen years was not reached. This probability was reached after just less than ten years. To achieve the required failure probability, at this load level, the dimensions of the specimens would have to be increased.

The intrinsic scatter in the results, described by the probability curve in Fig. 3, is particularly important as it will determine the quantitative evaluation of the minimum safety factors necessary for the composite structure. Recently experimental verification of this behaviour has been obtained, as shown in Fig.4. So as to reach inflection points within a few hours and demonstrate experimentally what is simulated in Fig. 3 identical unidirectional plates have been loaded to 96% of their nominal breaking load and kept at this load. Three typical examples of the damage curves obtained with such specimens are shown in Fig.4. Times to reach the inflection point varied from less than two hours to more than thirteen hours.

The scatter in reaching the inflection point, as shown by the simulations, was found in these experiments and show that identical composite structures showed

an intrinsic scatter in their behaviours. This has to be understood in assessing safety factors.

This type of behaviour has been discussed elsewhere for the simulated pressurisation of composite pressure vessels [8]. Damage accumulated in composite pressure vessels increases with time in an analogous fashion to that described above for plate specimens. A physical instability arises when the density of fibre breaks in the pressure vessel wall reaches its critical threshold and the regions of damage, initiated by fibre breaks and spread due to the viscoelastic behaviour of the matrix, begin to interfere. This is shown in Figure 5 which considers the effects of subjecting carbon fibre composite pressure vessels, designed to fail at 80 MPa (800 bars) to steady pressures.

The point of physical instability is shown by the point of inflection in the curve of damage accumulation for the simulated pressure vessel subjected to 70 MPa (700 bars). Although this point does not represent the burst of the pressure vessel it does represent a limit for its reliable use. It should be expected that inflection points would have been observed for lower pressures if the simulations had been continued for longer.

2.3 Discussion

The above study reveals that even the most stable form of carbon fibre reinforced composites, which are unidirectional plates, loaded in the fibre direction undergoes continuing damage processes. This has been demonstrated experimentally to be the case under both steady and cyclic loading. The fundamental mechanism controlling this damage is time dependent load transfer in the region of broken fibres to neighbouring intact fibres, due to matrix relaxation, which can then eventually break due to locally bearing an increased load.

Exactly similar behaviour to that seen in plate specimens is seen in filament wound carbon fibre composite pressure vessels. This process occurs under all types of loading and if it reaches a point where clusters of fibre breaks occur the structure becomes unreliable. The mechanisms involved mean that the composite structure fails by a sudden death scenario and a curve of residual strength would be almost horizontal until clustering of fibre breaks

occurs, at which point the composite would become unstable and failure would rapidly follow.

However, there are other processes which occur in these composites, which are also dependent on the viscoelastic nature of the matrix. No composite is made up of perfectly aligned fibres. Under load the relaxation of the matrix allows these fibres to become better oriented in the load direction and this both increases the rigidity and the strength of the composite in the fibre direction. This leads tests to measure residual strength to show that the properties of carbon fibre reinforced composite pressure vessels showing an increase in properties. However the basic mechanism of continuing fibre breaks cannot be nullified and if loading is continued there is a risk that unexpected failure will occur. The choice of a given safety factor has to take this into account.

Reinforcements other than carbon can also introduce other damage processes; in particular stress corrosion can cause the failure of glass fibres and is an intrinsic failure process in these fibres whereas this mechanism does not seem to exist in carbon fibres. Improvements, under load, in molecular orientation in aramid type fibres also mean that these processes can have an important effect on their long term use to a much greater extent than in carbon fibres.

The above model considers composite materials which are subjected to a uniform stress. This can be an issue, particularly with very thick walled pressure vessels of the type used to store hydrogen. However the mechanisms described above, which occur on the scale of the fibres, still operate in these vessels but are affected by the variation of the stress field in the composite wall.

A further development of this study has to take into account the effects of load transfer between load supporting plies in the composite pressure vessel and neighbouring plies, in which the fibres are not oriented in the major load direction. The above model can be considered as a first ply failure model but in reality the composite should be expected to be more resilient to damage as local clustering of fibre breaks will be mitigated by more compliant neighbouring plies which will limit the stress concentration effects of clusters of breaks.

When approaching failure, large macroscopic damage can become apparent, such as the debonding of tows of fibres. At this stage there are major

experimental difficulties for quantifying damage. However, this stage should never be reached in service. Finally it must be accepted that the structure of a pressure vessel is more than just the composite envelope, even though it is the composite which should, ideally, be determining ultimate mechanical properties. The failure of the liner or of the interface between the end bosses or of the end boss itself can also be a cause for the failure of a pressure vessel, although in these latter this should lead to a leakage rather than an explosion.

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Fig. 1: A quarter section of the representative volume element.

Figure 2: Comparison of simulated and experimental results of constant load tests, at 80% failure stress, with unidirectional specimens loaded in the fibre direction.

Figure 3: The times to instability are here shown as a Gaussian and accumulative probability curves of failure as a function of time in years.

Figure 4: AE curves for unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced epoxy loaded parallel to the fibre direction and held at 96% of median breaking load.

Figure 5: Simulated fibre breaks occurring in a pressure vessel held at constant pressure.

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